

A Review on Implementation of Affiliate trading platform using consumer response

Vrushali Shrawan Thombre¹, Vaibhav Ashok Dharnidhar², Pratiksha Nirvikar Adhau³,
Ankita Sanjay Dhunde⁴, Prof. Sharadha Chourasia⁵

¹Student, Department of IT, Nagpur Institute of Technology, Nagpur.

²Student, Department of IT, Nagpur Institute of Technology, Nagpur.

³Student, Department of IT, Nagpur Institute of Technology, Nagpur.

⁴Student, Department of IT, Nagpur Institute of Technology, Nagpur.

⁵Assitant Professor, Department of IT, Nagpur Institute of Technology.

Abstract: The rapid development of affiliate marketing, a performance based internet marketing practice, in the recent years has created a very competitive market. Companies need to constantly improve their affiliate programs to maintain a successful program and to keep affiliates loyal. Affiliate programs are a type of marketing where the partners or affiliates advertise products in several websites, social media platforms this type of marketing is based on performance, since compensation is usually calculated through the amount of clicks. The goal of proposed work is to build a functioning affiliate program for small retailers.

Keyword: Affiliate, Marketing, Socialmedia, etc.

I. INTRODUCTION

A digital marketing is a place where buyers and sellers are interacting and online retailers pay commission to an external website for generating sales or traffic through hits referrals. Additionally the affiliated marketing sometimes use conservative technique of publishing review of products or services offered by a partner. The supplier in e-commerce is short for business-to-business in electronic commerce, which is selling products or services between businesses through the internet via an online sales portal. The traditional method is processing orders manually – by telephone or e-mail but e-commerce orders can be processed digitally.

The customer of e-commerce will facilitate digital marketing as a new emerging trend to buy goods/products in the e-commerce website through the affiliate network or with the direct online e-commerce website. Affiliate marketing is a sales model where a company pays a third-party to sell their product and service. If a seller ever listened to a podcast or seen a social media influence promote a product, they are affiliate marketers. In exchange for recommending products or services to their audience, they get a commission off of any sale that results in their referral. Affiliates choose an affiliate marketing program, affiliates will receive a unique link or code that will allow the company to track every customer send their way. When a customer purchases the product through various platform or link, affiliates earn a commission.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Gerald L. Lohse, Steven Bellman, Eric J. Johnson (2000):-

Stated that Online retailing is a big business from the late 1998 to till now, so millions of people have ordered holiday gifts in the online and retailers has increased to upgrade their distribution of networks to increase the growth of retail marketing.

B. Chaffey et al. (2003):-

Stated the internet marketing strategy as “the definition of approach by which the internet marketing will support the marketing and business objectives of the organizations.” This study analyze in several marketing researches believe that the companies do not require separate internet marketing strategy.

C. Kotler and Armstrong (2008):- Defined that there are four major online marketing domains: (a) business-to-consumer, (b) business-to-business, (c) Consumer-to-Consumer.

D. Dr. Sonal Kala & Rajesh Kumar Sharma (2015):- Stated that Internet is the central-

hub for quick and rapid lifestyle, communication, connecting with people for official purposes. The interactions between custo-

mersandserviceprovidersinelectroniccommercethroughtheretailer'swebsite.StudymeasuredtherelationshipbetweenvariouscharacteristicsofonlineshoppingandcustomerpurchasebehaviourtowardsonlineshoppingandfutureofonlineshoppinginIndia.

E. Nielsen Reports(2017):-

thatpublishedtheoverallonlineshoppingtrendsinthelate2000.Totally,over875millionconsumershaveshoppedintheonline.The numberofonlineshoppershasalsoincreasedupto40%inthelasttwoyearsfrom2006to2008.

F. Sharma(2015):-explainedtheimportanceofInternetMarketingine-commerceandgivesabriefintroductionofInternetmarketing.AdvantagesofInternetadvertisinghavebeenexplainedwhilethevarious-e-commerce revenue models like CPA, CPL, CPM and CPI. The research examined various e-commerce websites like Flipkart, Snapdeal, Shopclues, Homeshop18, Fashion and Deals. He concludes that Internet Marketing is an essential tool for any company that wants to improve their revenue.

G. Prabhu and Satpathy(2015) analyzed the adaptability of the affiliate marketing in Indian scenario and to measure the future potential it holds. The study explained the entire process of affiliate in detail with the concept of Affiliate Marketing and also the weight on the affiliate program followed by various e-commerce websites

H. Obaidat, M.S., & Lorenz, P. (2016) Short form of electronic commerce is e-commerce, it is a type of innovative business model where individual or group or a firm can buy and sell one electronic network with support of internet. The other names of e-commerce are online commerce, web commerce, e-retail, e-tail and e-comm. But e-tail refers to any transactional processes around retail.

III.

PROPOSED METHODOLOGY

Affiliate marketing is promoting other people's products in return for a small commission for each sale. Firstly probably affiliate's seen headings marked "affiliate link" or "sponsored post" on many of the websites visit; or may be already a content writer the first step and signed up to an affiliate network first, find an affiliate program or network are interested in look at the program overview, including the type of products or services, payment methods, and commission they offer. If it appeals to you, sign up and wait for confirmation of your acceptance. Then, start creating content, adding the custom link the program provides. The link tracks when one of your users makes a purchase, and the affiliate earns a small commission. Companies or affiliate networks, where you register and choose the program that interests you. The programs are generally divided into categories to make selection easier. Once approved, start promoting your affiliate links on your website, in newsletters, on social media, and anywhere else you're permitted to share links. The network sends you a payment when reached the minimum payment level. Payment methods vary, and usually include PayPal, bank transfers, and checks.

A simplistic illustration of structure is shown in Figure. These modalities consist of steps:

Modules:-

- Administrator
- Login
- Registration
- Add Product
- DashBoard
- Change password

VI. CONCLUSION

Affiliate marketing is very effective at driving online sales. Every year it fuels approximately 15% to 20% of total online sales. The recent growth in the number of online businesses promises a lot of things as far as the scope of affiliate marketing is concerned in India. Small retailers also join this program and take knowledge about affiliated marketing and earn money by home and make his business internationally.

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